

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

REPORT ON NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN LEGISLATION ON REMOTE WORKING AND THE RIGHT TO DISCONNECT [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 1

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1. Introduction

Over the past decade, terms such as 'Industry 4.0' and 'Work 4.0' have become increasingly popular, eventually coming into common usage. The former refers to the set of changes that have affected technology, business and society in the 21st century thanks to the spread of tools that foster interconnectivity and automation.¹ The latter concerns a trend that has developed in response to the changes brought about by Industry 4.0, i.e. the set of transformations and innovations that have taken place in the labour field as a result of an increasing process of digitisation of work activities and the evolution of information and communication technologies.² Traditional ways of working, based on fixed locations and fixed hours, have been complemented by new forms based on the idea that, thanks to suitable technological supports, work can be performed anywhere and at any time.

The concept of remote working, i.e. work performed by the employee outside the traditional workplace, has thus gained ground. This trend began to develop in the United States in the 1970s,³ but despite predictions in the 1980s that it would become the dominant mode of working,⁴ it did not catch on for a long time, remaining a rarely used practice. The Covid-19 pandemic had significant repercussions in this regard. Indeed, as is well known, in order to contain the spread of the virus, governments adopted measures restricting freedom of movement. This led to a slowdown in non-essential production activities and a significant push in favour of the use of flexible working, i.e. work carried out without time or place constraints through the use of technological tools. According to available data, 48% of European workers worked from home at least once during the pandemic and 34% did so exclusively.⁵ It has thus gradually been acknowledged that remote working has many advantages for workers, as it can lead to greater autonomy, increased productivity and reduced commuting time. Therefore, remote working as a new model of ubiquitous and non-temporal work is now a reality.

However, problems may arise with regard to the effective enforcement of working hours and work-life balance. This is where the issue of the right to disconnect comes in. It takes the form of a remedy that allows the employee to remain selectively online, without any negative consequences in terms of remuneration or continuation of the employment relationship. Through it, therefore, the issue of employees' hyper-connection to company tools even outside working hours is addressed, given the

¹ On this concept, T. DEVEZAS, J. LEITÃO, A. SARYGULOV (eds), *Industry 4.0. Entrepreneurship and Structural Change in the New Digital Landscape*, Cham, 2017; P. BIANCHI, *4.0. La nuova rivoluzione industriale*, Bologna, 2018; A. USTUNDAG, E. CEVIKCAN (eds), *Industry 4.0: Managing The Digital Transformation*, Cham, 2018; B. SERGIET AL. (eds), *Understanding Industry 4.0: AI, the Internet of Things, and the Future of Work*, Bingley, 2019; E.G. POPKOVA, Y.V. RAGULINA, A.V. BOGOVIZ (eds), *Industry 4.0: Industrial Revolution of the 21st Century*, Cham, 2019.

² On this concept, A. CIPRIANI, A. GRAMOLATI, G. MARI (a cura di), *Il lavoro 4.0. La quarta rivoluzione industriale e le trasformazioni delle attività lavorative*, Firenze, 2018 and A. PERULLI, S. BELLOMO (eds), *Platform work and work 4.0: new challenges for labour law*, Padova, 2021.

³ EUROFOUND, INTERNATIONAL LABOUR OFFICE, *Working anytime, anywhere: The effects on the world of work*, Lussemburgo-Ginevra, 2017, p. 3.

⁴ A. TOFFLER, *The third wave*, New York, 1980.

⁵ EUROFOUND, *Telework and ICT-based mobile work: Flexible working in the digital age*, Luxembourg, 2020, p. 1.

harmful effects this phenomenon could have on employees' physical and mental health. The right to disconnect can thus be interpreted as the employee's right to unavailability, which protects him or her from uninterrupted work.

In the light of these developments, it is necessary to carry out a general assessment of the existing legal framework in order to understand what the law provides for and, more specifically, what obligations employers have to comply with and what kind of safeguards can be activated by employees. This report therefore focuses on national legislation concerning the various forms of remote working – i.e. work outside company premises – and the right to disconnect, taking into consideration the Italian legal system and the legal systems of other European countries. Where relevant, reference is made to international sources and to European Union legislation and case law. To this end, the interactions between national law, supranational law⁶ and international law⁷ as for labour law are preliminarily clarified.

2. Labour law between national, supranational and international regulations

As is widely known, labour law is the branch of private law that governs relations between employer and employee, labour relations and social and welfare policies. Given its very close connection to the business world and the development potential of a State, it is subject to regulation at the national level. However, over time, the influence of European Union law and international law has become increasingly relevant.

As far as European Union law is concerned, it should be recalled that the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community (1957) already included, among the four fundamental freedoms of the internal market, the freedom of movement for workers, which was intended to allow the labour force of the Member States to move freely to places where they could be recruited. One must consider, for example, that in the immediate post-war period, Italy, whose economy at the time was still strongly dependent on the agricultural sector, had an excess of workforce which, thanks precisely to the implementation of the aforementioned freedom, could be directed towards the central and northern European Member States, which were industrialised, needed workers and could not meet their needs exclusively at the domestic level.

Considering the framework in force today as a result of the Lisbon Treaty (concluded in 2007 and entered into force in 2009), Article 45 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) confirms that the freedom of movement for workers is protected within the Union. Such freedom entails the abolition of any discrimination based on nationality between workers of the Member States as regards employment, remuneration and other conditions of work and employment and the right, subject to limitations justified on grounds of public policy, public security or public health, to accept offers of employment actually made, to move freely within the territory of Member States for this purpose, to stay in a Member State for the purpose of employment and to remain in the territory of a Member State after having been employed in that State. Under Article 46 TFEU, the relevant rules in this area are laid down by means of directives or regulations,⁸ adopted through the ordinary legislative

⁶ European Union law is qualified as such given the fact that, by ratifying the Treaties that have marked the process of European integration, the Member States have chosen to transfer a part of their sovereign powers to the European Communities (before) and the European Union (now), in a manner that is innovative compared to what has been achieved with regard to other international organisations.

⁷ Reference is made to the branch of public law that deals mainly with relations between States, which are placed on an equal footing with each other due to their equal sovereignty.

⁸ For the sake of exhaustiveness, it should be recalled that European Union regulations are general in scope (i.e., they are addressed to indistinct categories of addressees, when not to all citizens), are mandatory in all their elements and are

procedure (and after consulting the European Economic and Social Committee) by the European Parliament and the Council, which may also, under Article 48 TFEU, adopt measures in the area of social security.

The notion of worker, for the purposes of the freedom at issue here, is not provided by the Treaties, but by the case law of the Court of Justice, in which it has been clarified that a worker is any person who undertakes genuine and effective work for which they are paid under the direction of someone else.⁹ Therefore, term workers, part-time workers or trainees also fall into this category.¹⁰

To this must be added that Union law also ensures the free movement of services with regard to services provided for remuneration that fall – by way of example – within the sphere of activities of an industrial character, activities of a commercial character, activities of craftsmen or activities of the professions (Article 57 TFEU). In this regard, a distinction must be made between the right of establishment and the freedom to provide services, depending on whether the activity is carried out continuously or occasionally by an economic entity in a Member State other than that of citizenship (or of incorporation, in the case of companies). In both cases, restrictions on the performance of the activities in question and forms of discrimination, primarily on grounds of nationality, are prohibited. Alongside this aspect, which has accompanied the process of European integration from the outset, there is another one, which has emerged over time and is more closely related to the development of a European Union social policy. Under Article 151 TFEU, the European Union and its Member States have as their objectives the promotion of employment, improved living and working conditions, so as to make possible their harmonisation while the improvement is being maintained, proper social protection, dialogue between management and labour, the development of human resources with a view to lasting high employment and the combating of exclusion. To this end, the Union and the Member States implement measures which take account of the diverse forms of national practices, in particular in the field of contractual relations, and the need to maintain the competitiveness of the Union economy. In the following Articles, it is clarified that the Union recognises and promotes the role of the social partners at its level, taking into account the diversity of national systems, and facilitates dialogue between the social partners, respecting their autonomy (Article 152 TFEU) and that the Union supports and complements the action of the Member States in a number of areas, including the improvement of the working environment, working conditions, equality between men and women with regard to labour market opportunities and the fight against social exclusion (Article 153, paragraph 1, TFEU). Furthermore, the European Commission promotes the consultation of management and labour at Union level and takes any relevant measure to facilitate their dialogue (Article 154 TFEU) and dialogue between the social partners at Union level may, if they so desire, lead to contractual relations, including agreements. They shall be implemented either in accordance with the procedures and practices specific to management and labour and the Member States or, within the fields covered by Article 153, and at the joint request of the signatory parties, by a Council decision on a proposal from the Commission (Article 155 TFEU).

directly applicable (i.e., once the *vacatio legis* period has elapsed since their publication in the Official Journal of the European Union, they apply in national legal systems as if they were national legal sources, without need to transpose them). By virtue of the principle of the supremacy of Community law, in the event of a conflict between Union regulation and national law, the former prevails, and the latter must be disapplied. Directives, on the other hand, are binding on the Member States to which they are addressed as to the result to be achieved and must be transposed into national legislation.

⁹ Among the many rulings dealing with this topic over time, see European Court of Justice, 3 July 1986, case 66/85, *Lawrie-Blum*.

¹⁰ For the relevant references, A. MONTANARI, *Libera circolazione dei lavoratori*, in F. CARINCI, A. PIZZOFERRATO (a cura di), *Diritto del lavoro dell'Unione europea*, III ed., Turin, 2021, p. 131.

Finally, because of the references that will be made to the right to disconnect and because it is considered by some to be the 21st century right to privacy,¹¹ it is worth recalling that the European Union ensures the right to the protection of personal data and that, to that end, the European Parliament and the Council, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure, lay down the rules relating to the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data by Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies, and by the Member States when carrying out activities which fall within the scope of Union law, and the rules relating to the free movement of such data (Article 16 TFEU).¹² By virtue of this competence, the European Union adopted Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (the so-called General Data Protection Regulation). In general, reference should be made to Article 24 of that Regulation, which, in identifying the principle of accountability, provides that, having regard to the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, and taking into account the risks represented by the likelihood and severity of the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure, and be able to demonstrate, that the processing is carried out in accordance with the Regulation. The measures must be reviewed and updated when necessary. With specific reference to the protection of workers, Article 88, entitled 'Processing of data in the context of the employment relationship,' comes to the fore. It provides that Member States may lay down, by law or by collective agreements, more specific rules to ensure the protection of the rights and freedoms with regard to the processing of employees' personal data in the context of employment relationships, in particular for the purposes of recruitment and performance of the employment contract. These rules should include appropriate and specific measures to safeguard human dignity, legitimate interests and fundamental rights of the people concerned, in particular with regard to the transparency of processing, the transfer of personal data within a group of undertakings or a group of undertakings carrying out a common economic activity, and workplace monitoring systems.

As regards international law, the role of the International Labour Organisation (ILO), founded in 1919 as an international organisation and today a specialised agency within the United Nations system, is of importance. Established with the aim of promoting better working conditions in the world, e.g. with regard to the regulation of working hours, the fixing of the maximum length of the working day and week, the fight against unemployment, the guarantee of a sufficient wage to ensure decent living conditions, the protection of workers against illness and accidents, the recognition of the principle of trade union freedom, the ILO has promoted the conclusion of international conventions in these and other matters. These are international treaties that are therefore not binding on the contracting States as a result of mere signature, requiring instead ratification in the manner prescribed by national laws. The distinctive feature of these treaties is that they are drafted through a modality unique to the ILO in the international system, i.e. through negotiations between governments and representatives at the ILO of trade unions and employers' associations (this is referred to as the tripartite structure of the ILO).

The ILO can also adopt recommendations, which do not determine any legal obligations, but identify useful guidelines for the application of principles and rules concerning labour relations.

¹¹ This will be discussed in the second part of the report.

¹² Under Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning them. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning them, and the right to have it rectified. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority.

PART I - Remote working: From homeworking to flexible working

3. Homeworking

In the history of industrial society, the idea of employment is closely linked to that of a physical place belonging to the employer in which work activities are carried out under the direct or indirect control of company management. Phenomena such as home working and teleworking, first, and flexible working (or, in Italy, agile working or *smart working*),¹³ later, have challenged this approach, allowing forms of remote working to gradually emerge.

With regard to home working, at the level of international law, reference can be made to the Home Work Convention, a treaty signed in 1996 within the ILO, which came into force in 2000 and has to date been ratified by 10 States.¹⁴ Home working is defined as work performed by an individual in their own home or other premises of their choice, other than an employer's premises, for remuneration, leading to the production of a product or service specified by the employer, irrespective of who provides the equipment, materials or other factors of production used. National legislation shall promote, as far as possible, equal treatment between homeworkers and other wage earners, in particular in relation to the right of homeworkers to establish or join organisations of their choice and to participate in the activities of such organisations, protection against discrimination in employment and occupation, protection in the field of occupational safety and health, remuneration, access to training, minimum age for admission to employment and maternity protection. National health and safety regulations must also apply to home-based work, taking into account its particular features, and must set out the conditions under which certain types of activity and the use of certain substances may be prohibited for health and safety reasons. An inspection system consistent with national laws and practices must be in place to ensure compliance with the laws and regulations applicable to home working.¹⁵

With regard to the Italian legal system, Law No. 877 of 18 December 1973 identifies as an homeworker anyone who, under a worker-employment bond, performs, in their own home or on premises available to them, also with the accessory help of members of their family who are cohabiting and dependent, but excluding paid labour and apprentices, paid work on behalf of one or more entrepreneurs, using raw or accessory materials and equipment belonging to them or to the entrepreneur themselves, even if supplied through third parties. Subordination occurs when the homeworker is required to comply with the directives of the entrepreneur as to the manner of performance, features and requirements of the service to be rendered in the partial performance, completion or entire processing of products covered by the client's activity.

¹³ As will be clarified later, in Italy, the regulation on flexible work is set out in the law on agile working, which is not considered as a different type of employment relationship, but rather as a particular mode of performing subordinate work introduced with the aim of increasing competitiveness and facilitating the reconciliation of work and life times (<https://www.lavoro.gov.it/strumenti-e-servizi/smart-working/Pagine/default>). Through such a mode, it is possible to alternate moments of work activity carried out on the employer's premises and moments of work activity carried out outside, without recourse to a fixed workstation, within the limits of daily and weekly working time set by law and by collective bargaining. In the course of time, the pseudo-anglicized term 'smart working', which however does not exist in English, has come into use to indicate this mode of work. Therefore, in what follows, the term 'smart working' will be used to refer to the Italian context and the term flexible working in the other cases.

¹⁴ They are Albania, Argentina, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Finland, Ireland, the Netherlands, Tajikistan and North Macedonia.

¹⁵ Specific guidelines on, for example, the establishment of competent authorities to draft and implement relevant national policies, supervision of homeworking, protection of the collective rights of homeworkers, remuneration, health and safety protection, working hours and rest periods can be found in the Home Work recommendation No. 184, adopted by the ILO in 1996.

According to the provisions of Articles L7412-1 to L7412-3 of the French *Code du travail*, a homemaker is anyone who performs, for a fixed fee, on behalf of one or more establishments, the service entrusted to them directly or through an intermediary and works alone, or with their spouse, partner in a civil solidarity pact, cohabitee, dependent children or assistant. It is not necessary to ascertain whether there is a legal relationship of subordination between the homemaker and the client, whether the homemaker works under the immediate and habitual supervision of the client, whether the premises in which the homemaker works and the equipment they uses belong to them, whether the homemaker themselves procures the ancillary materials and how many hours the homemaker works.

4. Teleworking

The concept of teleworking refers to an employee's work performed at a home connected to the company headquarters by means of information technology, thus overcoming the difficulties posed by commuting.¹⁶ Coined in the 1970s, the term 'telework' therefore refers to work performed outside the workplace with the support of technologies that enable a connection with the workplace context in which that work is performed.¹⁷ With the outbreak of the pandemic, teleworking has reached a turning point as more and more companies and institutions have introduced this way of working in an attempt to keep their employees safe while ensuring the continuity of business and activities.¹⁸

At European level, the reference point is the Framework Agreement concluded in Brussels on 16 July 2002 between organisations representing workers and employers.¹⁹ The Framework Agreement acknowledges that teleworking results from a voluntary choice by the employer and employee concerned. It may be included in the initial job description or result from a voluntary commitment made at a later date. In either case, the employer provides the necessary information in writing. If the employee expresses the wish to work as a teleworker, the employer may accept or refuse. If the employer accepts, the teleworker enjoys the same rights as a comparable person working on the company's premises. However, in order to take into account the peculiar nature of teleworking, specific supplementary agreements of a collective and/or individual nature may be adopted.

The employer retains responsibility for the protection of the health and workplace safety of the teleworker and is required to inform the teleworker of the company's occupational health and safety policies, particularly with regard to exposure to video display screens. In order to be able to verify that health and safety regulations are properly applied, the employer, employee representatives and/or competent authorities shall have access to the place where teleworking is carried out, subject, however, to the limits set by national regulations and collective agreements. Where the teleworker carries out the activity in their home, access is subject to prior notice and their consent.

In compliance with applicable legislation, collective agreements and company directives, the teleworker manages the organisation of their work time. Their workload and performance levels shall be equivalent to those of comparable workers performing activities on the company's premises.

The employer must take measures to prevent the isolation of the teleworker from other workers by ensuring the opportunity to meet regularly with colleagues and access company information. Teleworkers shall enjoy the same opportunities for access to training and career development as comparable workers performing activities on the company's premises and shall be subject to the same

¹⁶ F. LUCAFÒ, *Il rapporto di telelavoro. Regole giuridiche e prassi contrattuali*, Milan, 2007, p. 33-34.

¹⁷ M. MARRUCCI, *Orario di lavoro e riposi*, Milan, 2012, p. 200.

¹⁸ European Commission, *Telework in the EU before and after the COVID-19: where we were, where we head to*, 2020, p. 8.

¹⁹ The text is available at https://www.gms-srl.it/_resources/Telelavoro%20accordo_quadro_16_luglio_2002.pdf

evaluation criteria. In addition, they shall receive specific training on the technical working tools available to them and the peculiarities of teleworking. Additionally, they enjoy the same collective rights as workers working within the enterprise and their communication with workers' representatives should not be hindered.

This agreement was later implemented in Italy with the *Accordo interconfederale* of June 9, 2004, signed between the national business representative organisations (*Confindustria, Confartigianato, Confesercenti, Cna, Confapi, Confservizi, Abi, Agci, Ania, Apla, Casartigiani, Cia, Claii, Coldiretti, Confagricoltura, Confcooperative, Confcommercio, Confinterim, Legacoop, and Unci*) and the most representative trade unions (*Cgil, Cisl, and Uil*). The *Accordo interconfederale* commits all parties – businesses, workers and their respective representative bodies at all levels – associated with the signatory organisations to comply with the rules. It is therefore an Agreement that binds almost all private companies operating in Italy to respect its provisions.²⁰

Also in the case of Belgium, the regulations regarding structural telework find their source of inspiration in the Framework Agreement, on the basis of which trade unions and employers' organisations concluded Collective Labor Convention No. 85 of November 9, 2005, amended on February 27, 2008. On the other hand, regarding occasional telework, Articles 22-28 of the *loi concernant le travail faisable et maniable* of March 5, 2017, must be taken into consideration. In those articles, it is clarified that occasional telework is a form of organisation and/or performance of work under an employment contract based on the use of information technology, in which activities, that could also be carried out on the employer's premises, are performed outside those premises on an occasional and non-regular basis. More specifically, occasional telework may be carried out at the teleworker's home or at any other place chosen by the teleworker. The occasional teleworker enjoys the same rights as other workers in terms of working conditions and is subject to a workload and performance standards equivalent to those of similar workers employed on company premises. The worker may request occasional telework in the event of force majeure or for personal reasons that prevent them from providing the service on company premises, as long as the function or activity they perform is compatible with occasional telework. The worker must submit a request to the employer for occasional telework in advance, stating the reason. If the employer cannot comply with the request, they must inform the employee in writing of their reasons as soon as possible. The employer and the employee must agree on the arrangements for occasional teleworking, particularly with regard to whether the employer will provide the necessary equipment for occasional teleworking and technical assistance, whether the employee will be available during occasional teleworking, and whether the employer will cover the costs.

As for the United Kingdom, in 2003, the labour and management unions set out a Telework guidance based on the 2002 Framework Agreement.²¹

German law provides that telework stations are characterised by the presence of monitors and the fact that they are permanently installed by the employer in the employees' private/personal space. In this regard, the employer specifies the weekly working time agreed with the employees. The workstation is only set up if the employer and employee have defined the conditions for teleworking in an employment contract or agreement. The necessary equipment – including furniture, work equipment and communication facilities – must be provided and installed by the employer or a person appointed by the employer. The above definition is considered restrictive, given the fact that it cannot apply in

²⁰ <http://erc-online.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/2006-01444-EN.pdf>.

²¹ <http://erc-online.eu/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/2006-01458-EN.pdf>.

relation to cases of workers using – for example – a laptop to carry out their work. In this case, it is held to be a case of home working²².

In Greece, it was the pandemic that gave a decisive impetus to the development and reform of the relevant regulation. In the midst of the 2020 crisis, it was even envisaged that remote working could be arranged unilaterally by the employer, who was in any case under the obligation to bear the costs associated with the provision of the necessary equipment for the employee to carry out their work and to provide technical assistance. Today, the law defines telework as the provision of remote working, carried out with the aid of technology, in the context of a full-time, part-time, intermittent or other form of employment relationship, which may also be carried out at the employer's premises. Prior agreement between employee and employer is required for teleworking to be carried out. However, for reasons connected with the protection of public health, teleworking may be unilaterally introduced by decision of the employer or at the request of the employee, who is also granted a right to it in other cases (e.g. for health reasons or for protecting of the employee in the event of harassment).²³

As far as French law is concerned, Articles L1222-9 to L1222-11 of the *Code du travail* are devoted to telework. Pursuant to Article L1222-9, teleworking is defined as any form of organisation within the framework of which activity that could have been carried out on the employer's premises is performed by an employee outside those premises on a voluntary basis, using information and communication technologies. Teleworking must be implemented within the framework of a collective agreement or, if no such agreement exists, within the scope of a document drafted by the employer after consulting the social and economic committee – that is, the body representing employees within the enterprise – if such a committee exists. The collective agreement or document must specify the conditions for switching to teleworking and returning to performing in presence, how the employee may accept the conditions for implementing teleworking, how to control working hours or adjust the workload, how to determine the time slots when the employer can contact the teleworking employee, and the conditions for disabled workers and pregnant employees to access teleworking. The teleworker has the same rights as the employee who performs their work on the company's premises. An employer who refuses to grant the benefit of telework to an employee who occupies a suitable position for teleworking under the conditions stipulated by a collective agreement or, if no such agreement exists, by statute, must give reasons for their decision. In any case, refusal to accept a teleworking position is not a reason for termination of the contract. An injury that occurs at the teleworking location during the teleworker's professional activity is presumed to be a work-related injury. In the absence of a collective agreement or a document prepared by the employer, when the employee and employer agree to use teleworking, they must formalize their agreement by any means. Under Article L1222-10, the employer is required to: inform the teleworking employee of any restrictions on the use of computer equipment or tools or electronic communication services and of the penalties provided for failure to comply with such restrictions; give the employee priority where they intend to occupy or return to occupy a non-teleworking position that matches their professional qualifications and skills; inform the employee of the availability of such a position; and arrange an annual interview focusing on the employee's working conditions and workload. Finally, Article L1222-11 specifies that in exceptional circumstances, such as those resulting from a threat of epidemic, or in cases of force majeure, the use of teleworking may be considered as a necessary means to allow business continuity and ensure the protection of employees.

²² For this information, E. BAKIRTZI, *Remote work regulation during and after the pandemic in Greece and Germany: comparative legal frameworks and challenges for the future of work*, in *Italian Labour Law e-Journal*, 2022, p. 26.

²³ *Ivi*, p. 21-24.

Spanish Law 10/2021 de *trabajo a distancia* distinguishes between the concepts of remote working and teleworking. The former refers to a form of work organisation or work activity in which work is performed at the worker's home or at a place of worker's choice, for all or part of the working day, on a regular basis. The latter is a sub-category of the former, in that it takes the form of remote working carried out through the exclusive or predominant use of computer, telematic and telecommunication means and systems. Those who perform remote working enjoy the same rights as other workers and should not suffer any prejudice with regard to their conditions, including pay, job stability, working hours, training and professional promotion. The choice to implement forms of remote working is voluntary for both the employee and the employer and therefore requires the consent of both.

5. Flexible working and smart working

As for flexible working, at the European level, Directive (EU) 2019/1158 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on work-life balance for parents and carers must be recalled.

The directive sets minimum requirements aimed at achieving equality between men and women with regard to labour market opportunities and labour treatment by facilitating work-life balance for workers who are parents or caregivers.

To this end, the directive grants individual rights relating, *inter alia*, to flexible working arrangements for such workers, who may obtain an adjustment in the organisation of their work life, for example, through the use of remote working, flexible working schedules or reduced working hours. In this regard, Article 9 stipulates that Member States must take the necessary measures to ensure that workers with children up to a certain age, which must not be less than eight years old,²⁴ and caregivers have the right to request flexible working hours for care reasons. The duration of such flexible working arrangements may be subject to reasonable limitation.

Employers shall consider the requests and respond in light of both their own needs and those of the worker, giving reasons for any refusal or deferral.

When flexible working arrangements are temporary, at the end of the agreed period the worker has the right to return to the original working mode. The possibility of requesting a redetermination of the previous situation even before the end of the agreed period is granted, if a change of circumstances justifies this. Member States may make the right to request flexible working arrangements subject to a certain seniority in work or service, but not exceeding six months.

As far as Italy is concerned, the directive was transposed through Legislative Decree No. 105 of June 30, 2022. On this point, it is necessary to recall the regulations on agile working (also called smart working) in the private sector, laid down in Law No. 81 of May 22, 2017, since the relevant legislation as to flexible work was placed here.

Chapter II (Articles 18-24) of Law 81/2017 focuses on agile working.²⁵ It is provided that, in order to increase competitiveness and facilitate work-life balance, agile working is promoted as a mode of

²⁴ On this topic, one may also consider European Court of Human Rights, judgment of 19 February 2013, Appeal No. 38285/09, *García Mateos v. Spain*, concerning the case of a supermarket employee who had requested a reduction in her working hours because she had to take care of her son, who was less than six years old at the time. Spain was condemned for violation of the prohibition of discrimination, as well as for failure to respect the right to a fair trial. For an overview of the protection of workers' rights under the European Convention on Human Rights, V. MANTOUVALOU, *Labour Rights in the European Convention on Human Rights: An Intellectual Justification for an Integrated Approach to Interpretation*, in *Human Rights Law Review*, 2013, p. 1 ss.

²⁵ It should be emphasised that the concepts of teleworking and smart working (or agile working), while presenting undoubted similarities, do not refer to the same phenomenon. Although in both cases reference is made to ways of performing work based on agreement between the parties and the use of technological tools such as computers, smartphones and Internet connection, telework entails the observance of rigid working hours in the same way as for those

execution of the employment contract. It must be provided for by agreement between the parties and may be based on the organisation by phases, cycles and objectives and without precise constraints of time or place of work, with the possible use of technological tools for the performance of the work activity. The work activity is performed partly inside company premises and partly outside without a fixed location, within the limits only of maximum daily and weekly working time, as provided for by the law and collective bargaining.

The employer is responsible for the safety and proper functioning of the technological tools assigned to the worker.²⁶ In particular, as far as work safety is concerned, the employer shall deliver to the worker and the workers' safety representative, at least once a year, a written notice in which the general and specific risks related to the particular way the work is performed are identified. For their part, the worker is required to cooperate in the implementation of preventive measures set up by the employer.

A worker who performs agile work is entitled to an economic and regulatory treatment no inferior to that applied to workers who perform the same tasks exclusively within the company premises. They may be granted the right to lifelong learning and periodic certification of skills. In addition, they are entitled to protection against accidents at work and work-related illnesses caused by risks connected to work performed outside the company premises and protection against accidents occurring during the normal journey to and from the place of residence to the place chosen for the performance of work outside the company premises.

Article 18, paragraph 3-bis, provides that employers are required to give priority to requests to perform work in agile mode from employees with children up to twelve years of age, or without any age limit in the case of children with disabilities. The same priority is granted by the employer to requests from workers with disabilities in a proven situation of ascertained seriousness. A worker requesting to take advantage of agile working may not be sanctioned, demoted, dismissed, transferred or subjected to any other organisational measure having direct or indirect negative effects on working conditions. Any measure adopted in violation of this provision is considered retaliatory or discriminatory and, therefore, null and void.

Under Article 19 of Law 81/2017, the agreement relating to the agile work modality is to be stipulated on a temporary or fixed-term basis and in writing for the purposes of administrative correctness and proof and it must regulate the performance of the work carried out outside the company premises, also with regard to the forms of exercise of the employer's managerial power and the tools used by the worker, the worker's rest times and the technical and organisational measures necessary to ensure the worker's disconnection from the technological work equipment.

However, during the pandemic emergency phase and with regard to the private sector only, a simplified procedure was introduced for sending electronically a special form to the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies, listing the names of workers and the date of termination of agile work, instead of transmitting individual agreements (Article 90 of Decree-Law No. 34 of 19 May 2020, converted with amendments by Law No. 77 of 17 July 2020). The validity of these rules was extended until 31 December 2022 by the so-called Aiuti-bis Decree (Art. 25-bis of Decree-Law No. 115 of 9 August 2022, converted with amendments into Law No. 142 of 21 September 2022).

who work in presence and the use of a fixed workstation in a place other than the company headquarters. This phenomenon is regulated (in Italy) by the above-mentioned *Accordo interconfederale*. Smart working is based on flexible hours, does not require a fixed location and is regulated (in Italy) by Law 81/2017. On this topic, M. MARTONE, *Lo smart working nell'ordinamento italiano*, in *Diritto Lavori Mercati*, 2018, p. 293 ss.

²⁶ It should be noted that in the *Commissione Interpelli's* response to Interrogation No. 1/2023, the Ministry of Labor clarified that in order to ensure health and safety conditions in the workplace in favour of smart working workers too, the employer may appoint more than one competent physician to ensure health surveillance. For more information, <https://www.lavoro.gov.it/documenti-e-norme/interpelli/Documents/Interpello-1-2023.pdf>.

According to the Budget Law 2023 (Article 1, paragraph 306 of Law 197 of 29 December 2022), until 31 March 2023, as for frail workers,²⁷ public and private employees, the employer ensures the possibility of performing the working activity in the form of smart working also through the assignment to a different task included in the same category or area of classification, as defined by the collective labour agreements in force, without any reduction of the remuneration.

In Belgium, it is worth mentioning the *Convention collective* No. 162 of 27 September 2022, concluded by the representative organisations of the social partners, which states that an employee whose contract of employment lasts at least 6 months has the right to request a flexible work agreement for a maximum of 12 months, which may be renewed on the basis of an agreement with the employer or a sectoral or company collective agreement. The agreement may concern teleworking, an adjustment of working hours (e.g. the granting of flexible working time) or a reduction in working hours. The employee has the right to apply to take care of children up to the age of 12 or to provide care or assistance to a family member. While taking into account the needs expressed by employees, the employer may base their decision on economic or organisational reasons to justify any postponement or refusal, or to propose an alternative solution.

As for the United Kingdom, reference may be made to the Employment Rights Act 1996, as amended over time, which, in Part 8A on Flexible Working, makes it clear that a worker may request a change in the terms and conditions of employment from the employer if the change is related, *inter alia*, to the place of performance, with a choice between their home and the employer's designated place. The employer may refuse only for reasons concerning the fact that the change would entail additional costs, an adverse effect on the ability to satisfy customers, an inability to reorganise the work of existing staff, an inability to hire additional staff, a negative impact on the quality of work, a negative impact on performance, a shortage of work during the periods when the employee intends to work, or because structural changes are planned, and for other reasons specified in the relevant regulations. The Flexible Working Regulations of 2014 stipulate that the request must be made in writing and dated and must indicate whether a similar request has been made in the past and, if so, when.

PART II - The right to disconnect

6. Working time and the right to rest

As regards working time and the worker's right to rest, there is plenty of European Union legislation that should be taken into consideration. At the level of sources of primary law, it is interesting to note that the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, under Article 31, paragraph 2, provides that every worker has the right to a limitation of maximum working hours, to daily and weekly rest periods and to paid annual leave, thus implementing the approach that had already come out of the directives mentioned below and providing greater protection to these rights.²⁸

As regards sources of secondary law, some general hints can be found in Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work. As a matter of fact, the Directive defines principles concerning the prevention of occupational risks, the protection of safety and health, the elimination of risk and

²⁷ These are those who suffer from the pathologies and meet the conditions identified in the Decree of the Minister of Health referred to in Article 17, paragraph 2 of Decree-Law no. 221 of 24 December 2021 (converted with amendments into Law no. 11 of 18 February 2022).

²⁸ P. ICHINO, L. VALENTE, *L'orario di lavoro e i riposi. Artt. 2107-2109*, II ed., Milan, 2012, p. 30-31. It should be recalled *en passant* that, following the reform brought about by the Treaty of Lisbon and by virtue of Article 6, paragraph 1, of the Treaty on European Union, the Charter of Fundamental Rights has the same legal value as the Treaties. Thus, it is a source of primary law of the Union.

accident factors, the informing, consultation, balanced participation in accordance with national laws and/or practices and training of workers and their representatives, as well as general guidelines for the implementation of the said principles. Among them, there is the principle according to which the employer must adapt the work to the individual, especially as regards the design of workplaces, the choice of work equipment and the choice of working and production methods, with a view, in particular, to alleviating monotonous work and work at a predetermined work-rate and to reducing their effect on health. In general, there is an obligation on the employer to avoid risks, assess those that cannot be avoided and combat them at the source.

With specific regard to the issues of working time and rest periods, originally, through Council Directive 93/104/EC of 23 November 1993 concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time, it was stipulated that the Member States of the Union were to take the necessary measures to ensure that each worker, during each 24-hour period, was granted a minimum rest period of 11 consecutive hours, a rest break where the daily working time exceeded six hours, and a minimum uninterrupted rest period of 24 hours for each seven-day period. In addition, the Member States, in order to ensure the safety and health protection of workers, were to ensure that the weekly working time was limited and that the average working time for each seven-day period did not exceed 48 hours, including overtime. Article 13 of the directive, concerning the pattern of work, referred to the principle already mentioned above that an employer who planned to organise work according to a certain pattern had to take account of the need to adapt work to human beings, placing an obligation on the Member States to define the measures necessary for that purpose.

Directive 93/104/EC was later repealed by directive 2003/88/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 November 2003 concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time. It defines working time as any period during which the worker is working, at the employer's disposal and carrying out his activity or duties, in accordance with national laws and/or practice. The provisions of the previous directive are essentially confirmed here.²⁹

In this regard, the Court of Justice clarified that the concept of working time covers the entirety of periods of stand-by time, including those according to a stand-by system, during which the constraints imposed on the worker are such as to affect, objectively and very significantly, the possibility for the latter freely to manage the time during which their professional services are not required and to pursue their own interests.³⁰ Conversely, where the constraints imposed on a worker during a specific period of stand-by time do not reach such a level of intensity and allow them to manage their own time, and to pursue their own interests without major constraints, only the time linked to the provision of work actually carried out during that period constitutes working time.³¹

Furthermore, the Court held that Directive 2003/88/EC precludes legislation of a Member State which, as interpreted by national case-law, does not impose an obligation on employers to establish a system for measuring the duration of workers' daily working time. Indeed, the objective and reliable determination of the number of hours worked per day and week is essential for establishing, on the one hand, whether the maximum weekly working time has been complied with and, on the other

²⁹ The transposition of this directive into Italian law took place with Legislative Decree No 66 of 8 April 2003, concerning the implementation of Directives 93/104/EC and 2000/34/EC concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time.

³⁰ European Court of Justice, 9 March 2021, case C-580/19, *Stadt Offenbach am Main (Période d'astreinte d'un pompier)*, paragraph 38. Furthermore, see European Court of Justice, 21 February 2018, case C-518/15, *Matzak*, paragraph 66 and 9 September 2021, case C-107/19, *Dopravní podnik hl. m. Prahy*, paragraph 34.

³¹ European Court of Justice, 9 March 2021, case C-344/19, *Radiotelevizija Slovenija (Période d'astreinte dans un lieu reculé)*, paragraphs 37-38.

hand, whether the minimum daily and weekly rest periods, as defined by the Directive, have been complied with during each 24-hour period as regards daily rest or during the reference period.³²

7. The right to disconnect: doctrinal hints

The first hints as to the existence of a right to disconnect came from the French legal scholar Jean-Emmanuel Ray, a professor at the Université Panthéon-Sorbonne, who has argued since 2002 that the law, case law and above all collective agreements should recognise a right to isolation and disconnection aimed at allowing workers a real, continuous and effective period of rest to cope with the harmful effects of being connected outside working hours.³³ Clarified that the right to disconnect should be regarded as the 21st century right to privacy, the aim is to preserve the health and family and social life of the worker, counteracting the phenomenon of dilution of the boundary between private and working life.³⁴

Subsequently, French legal scholars have distinguished between two categories of the right to disconnect: the right to disconnect at work, intended as a remedy against hyper-connection resulting from the excessive use of technological devices, and the right to disconnect from work, to ensure respect for rest time, the protection of health and the preservation of the personal sphere³⁵.

The wealth of literature on the subject confirms the scholarly community's particular interest in this new concept.³⁶ However, it should be noted that it is precisely legal scholars that have complained of the ineffectiveness of this right arising from the difficulty of establishing whether the right to disconnect is an actual right or rather a duty incumbent on the employer.³⁷

There are therefore those who have identified it as the worker's right to be .unavailable, emphasising that it is certainly not the right to stay offline or to pull the plug, as the media have dubbed it in their search for the effect on the reader. Instead, it is the right to remain selectively on the net, preventing oneself from being searched for at certain times of the day in order to protect the worker from non-stop work or from working hours that generate or encourage forms of workaholism.³⁸

There are those who describe it as a remedy to protect workers against overworking and the risk of always being connected: a remedy that, to be concretely guaranteed, requires a structured management of human resources and a correct distribution of working hours in relation to the workload.³⁹

³² European Court of Justice, 14 May 2019, case C-55/18, *CCOO*, paragraphs 44, 71.

³³ J.-E. RAY, *De la sub/ordination à la sub/organisation*, in *Droit Social*, 2002, p. 5.

³⁴ J.-E. RAY, *Naissance et avis de décès du droit à la déconnexion, le droit à la vie privée du XXIe siècle*, in *Droit Social*, 2002, p. 939.

³⁵ L. MOREL, *Le droit à la déconnexion en droit français La question de l'effectivité du droit au repos à l'ère du numérique*, in *Labour & Law Issues*, 2017, p. 6.

³⁶ For some hints, A. ROMEO, *Il diritto alla disconnessione del lavoratore tra invadenze tecnologiche e nuove modalità della prestazione*, in *Rivista giuridica del lavoro*, 2019, p. 671 ss.; A. FENOGLIO, *Il tempo di lavoro nella new automation age: un quadro in trasformazione*, in *Rivista italiana di diritto del lavoro*, 2018, p. 646 ss.; E. DAGNINO, *Il diritto alla disconnessione nella legge n. 81/2017 e nell'esperienza comparata*, in *Diritto delle relazioni industriali*, 2017, p. 1024 ss.; E. SENA, *Lavoro agile e diritto alla disconnessione: l'incidenza delle nuove tecnologie sulle modalità di esecuzione della prestazione di lavoro*, in *Diritto del mercato del lavoro*, 2018, p. 245 ss.

³⁷ In this regard, V. ZEPPELLI, *Disconnessione: un'occasione mancata per il legislatore?*, in *Rivista giuridica del lavoro e della previdenza sociale*, 2019, p. 314 and R. ZUCARO, *Il diritto alla disconnessione tra interesse collettivo e individuale. Possibili profili di tutela*, in *Labour & Law Issues*, 2019, p. 231.

³⁸ D. POLETTI, *Il c.d. diritto alla disconnessione nel contesto dei "diritti digitali"*, in *Responsabilità civile e previdenza*, 2017, p. 8 ss.

³⁹ C. TIMELLINI, *Il diritto alla disconnessione nella normativa italiana sul lavoro agile e nella legislazione emergenziale*, in *Lavoro Diritti Europa*, 4/2021, p. 2-3.

There is no shortage of those who place more emphasis on the duty incumbent on the employer because of the intimate connection between the right to disconnect and the rest time to be enjoyed by the employee. Given the inalienability of daily rest, weekly rest and holidays, which serve to protect the worker, it seems easy to argue that disconnection, in addition to being a right, is also a duty with which the employer must comply.⁴⁰

8. The right to disconnect: regulatory profiles

As regards Italy, as mentioned above, Law No. 81 of 22 May 2017 introduced agile working, without, however, recognising a right to disconnect that can be directly relied upon by the worker. On the contrary, pursuant to its Article 19, this law has deferred to the agreement regulating this modality of work the definition of the worker's rest time and the technical and organisational measures necessary to ensure disconnection from the work's technological devices.

Following the Covid-19 pandemic and the need to resort to smart working, the Italian legislator returned to the issue with Law No. 61 of 6 May 2021, converting Decree-Law No. 30 of 13 March 2021, regarding urgent measures to deal with the spread of Covid-19 and support measures for workers with minor children in distance learning or quarantine. Under Article 2, paragraph 1-ter, it is provided that, without prejudice, for the civil service, to the regulation of agile work set by national collective agreements, the worker who performs the activity in agile mode has the right to disconnect from technological instruments and IT platforms, in conformity with any agreements signed by the parties and without prejudice to any agreed stand-by periods. The exercise of this right may not affect the employment relationship or remuneration.

In addition, reference must be made to the national collective labour agreement for staff in the Education and Research sector 2016/2018. Article 22(4)(c) provides that the general criteria for the use of technological working tools outside working hours are subject to supplementary agreements at school and educational institution level.

In addition, mention may be made of the national collective labour agreement for middle managers and staff in professional areas employed by credit, financial and instrumental enterprises of 19 December 2019. It provides that working in agile mode is carried out within the limits of daily and weekly working time set by the collective agreement, in compliance with the rules on breaks and rest. Workers can deactivate their connection devices so as not to receive company communications beyond working hours or during legitimate periods of absence.

Finally, the national protocol on agile working, signed on 7 December 2021 at the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies, stipulates that agile working requires the stipulation in writing of an individual agreement that identifies, *inter alia*, the worker's rest time and the technical and/or organisational measures necessary to ensure disconnection. In particular, pursuant to Article 3, agile working may be divided into time slots, identifying, in each case, the disconnection period in which the worker does not perform work. Specific technical and/or organisational measures must be adopted to guarantee the disconnection time band and, in cases of legitimate absences (e.g. illness, accidents, paid leave, holidays, etc.), the worker may deactivate their connection devices. If company communications are received, the employee is not obliged to take them up before the planned return to work.

In France, since 2016, a provision has been introduced in the *Code du travail*, in Article L. 2242-17, paragraph 7, according to which the annual negotiation on professional equality between women and men and on the quality of life and working conditions covers (also) the terms and conditions for the

⁴⁰ R. PERRONE, *Il «diritto alla disconnessione» quale strumento di tutela di interessi costituzionalmente rilevanti*, in *federalismi.it*, 20 dicembre 2017, p. 18.

full exercise by employees of the right to disconnect and the implementation by the company of measures aimed at regulating the use of digital tools, in order to ensure respect for rest and holiday time, as well as personal and family life. In the absence of an agreement, the employer must draw up a document defining the terms and conditions for the exercise of the right to disconnect, also providing for the implementation of training and awareness-raising measures for employees and management staff on the judicious use of digital tools.⁴¹

In Belgium, Article 16 of the *loi relative au renforcement de la croissance économique et de la cohésion sociale* of 26 March 2018 defers the issue to employer-initiated consultation in order to ensure respect for rest periods, annual leave and other leaves for workers and to preserve work-life balance.

In Germany, there is no legal framework concerning the right to disconnect. However, over the years, a model has emerged based on measures developed by individual companies following discussions with the social partners (the so-called corporate self-regulatory approach), aimed at limiting the employer's possibility to contact employees outside working hours.⁴²

In Greece, Article 67 of Law 4808/2021 states, *inter alia*, that the teleworker enjoys the right to disconnect, which consists of the right to completely abstain from carrying out their work and, in particular, not to communicate digitally and not to answer telephone calls, e-mails or any other form of communication outside working hours and during compulsory leave. Any form of discrimination against the teleworker for exercising this right is prohibited. The provision of the necessary technical and organisational means to ensure the teleworker's disconnection from the digital communication and work tools must be provided for in the teleworking contract and shall be the subject of an agreement between the employer and the representatives of the employees of the undertaking or establishment. In the absence of such an agreement, the means in question shall be established by the employer and communicated by the latter to all employees.⁴³

In Spain, Article 88 of the *ley orgánica 3/2018 de Protección de Datos Personales y garantía de los derechos digitales* stipulates that civil servants have the right to digital disconnection so that rest time, leave and holidays, as well as private and family life, are guaranteed outside the working hours set by law or conventionally. The terms for exercising this right must take into account the nature and purpose of the employment relationship and reconcile work commitments with private and family life and are subject to the provisions of collective bargaining or, failing that, to agreement between the company and the workers' representatives. The employer, having consulted the latter, shall draw up an internal policy defining the modalities for exercising the right to disconnect and training and awareness-raising measures for staff on the judicious use of technological tools in order to avoid the risk of computer fatigue. In particular, the right to digital disconnection must be preserved in cases of total or partial remote work and at the employee's home in connection with the use of technological tools for work purposes. Furthermore, Article 18 of *ley 10/2021 de trabajo a distancia* provides that remote workers have the right to digital disconnection outside working hours under the terms set by Article 88 of *ley orgánica 3/2018*. Confirming the provisions of Article 88 regarding the employer's obligations, Article 18 also provides that collective agreements may establish the appropriate means

⁴¹ On France and Spain, L. LEROUGE, F. TRUJILLO PONS, *Contribution to the study on the 'right to disconnect' from work. Are France and Spain examples for other countries and EU law?*, in *European labour law journal*, 2022, p. 450 ss.

⁴² EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT RESEARCH SERVICE, *The right to disconnect*, p. 4 disponibile in https://www.telepolis.pl/images/2021/01/EPRS_BRI2020642847_EN.pdf e P.M. SECUNDA, *The Employee Right to Disconnect*, in *Notre Dame Journal of International & Comparative Law*, 2019, p. 29-30.

⁴³ In this regard, E. BAKIRTZI, *cit.*, p. 24

and measures to guarantee the effective exercise of the right to disconnect in remote work and the proper organisation of the working day so that that organisation is compatible with rest periods.⁴⁴

To confirm the crucial importance that the issue of the right to disconnect has gained, one initiative of the European Parliament can be recalled. In a resolution adopted on 21 January 2021, that institution made recommendations to the European Commission regarding that right.⁴⁵ According to the European Parliament, digitisation and digital tools have brought many benefits to employers and employees in terms of flexibility, autonomy, work-life balance and reduced travel time, but they have also raised ethical, legal and employment issues, specifically with regard to work intensification and extended working hours. The always-connected culture can undermine workers' fundamental rights, compromising, among other things, their physical and mental health, safety at work and well-being. The use of digital tools for prolonged periods can also result in reduced concentration and cognitive and emotional overload, as well as lead to isolation, technology dependency, sleep deprivation, emotional exhaustion, anxiety and burnout.

In this context, the right to disconnect arises as “a fundamental right which is an inseparable part of the new working patterns in the new digital era” and “an important social policy instrument at Union level to ensure protection of the rights of all workers”.⁴⁶ It makes it possible for workers to refrain from carrying out electronic work tasks, activities and communications outside working hours, including rest periods, official and annual holidays, maternity, paternity and parental leave without any negative consequences.

For this reason, the European Parliament emphasised the need to achieve a proper and efficient use of digital tools for work purposes and requested the European Commission to submit a proposal for a Union directive on minimum standards and conditions to ensure that workers can effectively exercise their right to disconnect, as well as a legislative framework to establish minimum requirements on remote work throughout the Union, ensuring that teleworking does not undermine the employment conditions of teleworkers.

Regarding the first issue, the European Parliament also formulated a proposal for a directive on the right to disconnect. Having identified the legal basis in Article 153 TFEU,⁴⁷ the European Parliament confirms that the right to disconnect is the right of workers not to engage in work-related activities or communications by means of digital tools, directly or indirectly, outside working time and not to respond to employer requests outside working hours. It should apply to all workers and all sectors, therefore both in the public and private sectors (recitals n. 10-11 and Articles 1-2).

Member States must ensure that employers take the necessary measures to provide workers with the means to exercise their right to disconnect and set up an objective, reliable and accessible system enabling the duration of time worked each day by each worker to be measured (Article 3). Furthermore, employers must provide each worker in writing with clear, sufficient and adequate information on their right to disconnect (Article 7). Member States must lay down certain minimum guarantees, concerning the practical arrangements for disconnecting from digital tools for work purposes, the system for measuring working time, health and safety assessments, the criteria for

⁴⁴ For further insights from a comparative perspective, A. FENOGLIO, *Il diritto alla disconnessione del lavoratore agile*, in G. ZILIO GRANDI, M. BIASI (a cura di), *Commentario breve allo Statuto del lavoro autonomo e del lavoro agile*, Padova, 2018, p. 549 ss.

⁴⁵ European Parliament resolution of 21 January 2021 with recommendations to the Commission on the right to disconnect (2019/2181(INL)).

⁴⁶ *Ibidem*.

⁴⁷ The European Parliament recalls Article 153, paragraph 1, letters a), (b) and i), TFEU, under which the Union shall support and complement the activities of the Member States with regard to the improvement of the working environment to protect workers' health and safety, working conditions and equality between men and women with regard to labour market opportunities and treatment at work.

granting employers a derogation from the obligation to implement workers' right to disconnect, the criteria for establishing how compensation for work performed outside working hours is to be calculated, and the awareness-raising measures, including on-the-job training, to be taken by employers (Article 4). In addition, Member States must ensure that discrimination, less favourable treatment, dismissal and other detrimental measures by employers on the grounds that a worker has exercised or attempted to exercise the right to disconnect are prohibited, giving workers the possibility to bring an action before a court or another competent authority if they believe they have been dismissed or have suffered another adverse consequence for these reasons (Article 5). A right to appeal must be provided where the right to disconnect has been violated (Article 6). Effective, proportionate and dissuasive sanctions must be introduced for violations of the provisions concerning the right to disconnection (Article 8).

Despite this, the European Commission has not followed up on the requests of the European Parliament.

9. The proposal for a directive on improving working conditions in platform work

To conclude this excursus, it is worth pointing out a possible further development, which is related to the spread of the so-called gig economy as an economic model based on on-call, occasional and temporary work.⁴⁸ In this framework, the worker is a freelancer, carrying out an on-demand activity that should guarantee more flexibility so as to allow them to reconcile work-related and non-work-related commitments. The professions affected by this phenomenon are the most varied: from riders who deliver orders of various kinds to Internet site developers, from marketing experts to graphic designers, from copywriters to photographers. The phenomenon is expanding rapidly thanks to digital work platforms that take advantage of the services offered by these workers. This is the case of Uber, Foodora, Deliveroo, Fiverr and many other entities that, as noted by the European Commission, promote innovative services and new business models, offering many people, including those who find it difficult to enter the labour market (young people, migrants, people with disabilities), the opportunity to work and earn.⁴⁹

The problems that arise in connection with this can be traced back to the correct legal qualification of the employment relationship that is established between the worker and the platform,⁵⁰ the role that IT systems play in assigning tasks and making decisions in relation to workers, the need for traceability and transparency with regard to working conditions and access to social protection, and, in general, the protection of workers' rights, first and foremost the right to disconnect.

This is the background to the proposal for a directive on the improvement of working conditions in platform work, tabled by the European Commission in December 2021. Through it, multiple objectives would be pursued, consisting of guaranteeing that workers can have their correct employment status recognised in the light of their actual relationship with the digital work platform,

⁴⁸ In this regard, V. DE STEFANO, *The Rise of the "Just-in-Time Workforce": On-Demand Work, Crowdsourcing, and Labor Protection in the "Gig Economy"*, in *Comparative Labor Law & Policy Journal*, 2016, p. 471 ss.; O. LOBEL, *The Gig Economy & the Future of Employment and Labor Law*, in *University of San Francisco Law Review*, 2017, p. 51 ss.; A. STEWART, J. STANFORD, *Regulating work in the gig economy: What are the options?*, in *The Economic and Labour Relations Review*, p. 361 ss.

⁴⁹ Proposal for a directive of the European Parliament and the Council on improving working conditions in platform work, COM(2021) 762 final, p. 1.

⁵⁰ In general on this topic, A. DONINI, *Il lavoro digitale su piattaforma*, in *Labour & Law Issues*, 2015, p. 49 ss.; G. PACELLA, *Il lavoro tramite piattaforma digitale nella giurisprudenza dei Paesi di civil law*, in *Labour & Law Issues*, 2019, p. 15 ss.; E. RAIMONDI, *Il lavoro nelle piattaforme digitali e il problema della qualificazione della fattispecie*, in *Labour & Law issues*, 2019, p. 60 ss.

ensuring the accountability of the digital platform with regard to algorithmic work management profiles and protecting workers' rights.

If approved, the directive will apply to digital workplaces that organise work through digital platforms carried out in the Union, regardless of their place of establishment and the law otherwise applicable. They are identified pursuant to Article 2 as any natural or legal person providing a commercial service which is provided, at least in part, at a distance through electronic means, at the request of a recipient of the service, and that involves, as a necessary and essential component, the organisation of work performed by individuals, irrespective of whether that work is performed online or in a certain location.

In light of the latter requirement, the question arises as to exactly what the worker's employment status is. Article 3 defers this to appropriate procedures set up by the Member States but makes it clear that facts relating to the actual performance of the work must be taken into account, taking into account the use of algorithms in the organisation of work through digital platforms, regardless of how the relationship is classified in any contractual agreement between the parties involved. The contractual relationship between the platform and the person performing work through it is presumed to be an employment relationship; however, Member States are required to ensure that this legal presumption can be rebutted in judicial and administrative proceedings by placing the *onus probandi* on the platform, if it claims that it is not in fact an employment relationship (Articles 4-5).

Assessments of the proposal emphasise that it goes in the direction of recognising that the higher the level of automation of the monitoring and decision-making systems, the greater the likelihood that the person performing the work is subordinate to the platform and, therefore, should be considered an employee.⁵¹ Therefore, it can be said that the proposal seems to reaffirm a principle of primacy of facts with regard to the determination of the relationship that binds the worker to the platform.⁵²

Platforms will be required to inform workers about automated monitoring systems used to control, supervise or evaluate the work performance and automated decision-making systems used to make or support decisions that significantly affect the workers' working conditions (e.g., concerning their access to work assignments, their earnings, their safety and health, their working hours). The information shall concern in particular the fact that they systems are in use, the categories of decisions taken by the systems and the main parameters underlying these decisions. The information shall be provided no later than the first working day, in the event of substantial changes and at any time at the request of digital platform workers and shall be made available to digital platform workers' representatives and national labour authorities at their request. Personal data relating to digital platform workers may not be processed if they are not intrinsically linked to and strictly necessary for the performance of the contract, in particular if they are personal data relating to the emotional or psychological state of the worker (Article 6).

Particularly noteworthy is Article 7, devoted to human monitoring of automated systems, which provides that platforms shall periodically monitor and assess the impact on working conditions of individual decisions made or supported by automated decision-making and monitoring systems, and that they shall not use such systems in a way that puts undue pressure on digital platform workers or otherwise endanger the physical and mental health of digital platform workers. Platforms will have to ensure sufficient human resources to monitor the impact of individual decisions and, under Article 8, will have to provide workers with an explanation for decisions made by automated systems

⁵¹ A. ALOISI, N. POTOCKA-SIONEK, *De-gigging the labour market? An analysis of the 'algorithmic management' provisions in the proposed Platform Work Directive*, in *Italian Labour Law e-Journal*, 2022, p. 33.

⁵² V. DE STEFANO, *The EU Commission's proposal for a Directive on Platform Work: an overview*, in *Italian Labour Law e-Journal*, 2022, p. 1 ss. Furthermore, G. BRONZINI, *La proposta di Direttiva sul lavoro nelle piattaforme digitali tra esigenze di tutela immediata e le sfide dell'"umanesimo digitale"*, in *Lavoro Diritti Europa*, 2022, p. 2 ss.

by referring them to a contact person in order to clarify the facts, circumstances and reasons for the decisions. If, on the basis of the decision, the worker's account is restricted, suspended or terminated, or the worker is not paid, or if the decision relates to the worker's contractual situation or has similar effects, the platforms will have to give the worker a written explanation. If the worker is not satisfied, they may ask the platform to reconsider the decision, receiving a reasoned reply within a short time.

Platforms will have to declare the work performed by workers to national labour and social protection authorities, sharing the relevant data (Article 11), and workers will have to have access to effective and impartial dispute resolution mechanisms, benefiting from a right of redress in the event of violations of their rights under the directive (Article 13). In this regard, it is also envisaged that representatives of persons performing work through digital platforms or other legal entities that have a legitimate interest in defending the rights of those persons will be able, with those persons' approval, to initiate judicial or administrative proceedings to enforce their rights or obligations under the directive (Article 14). The possibility for workers to contact and communicate with each other, as well as to be contacted by their representatives, through the digital infrastructure of the platforms or equally effective means, without the platforms monitoring these communications, will have to be guaranteed (Article 15). In proceedings relating to complaints concerning the correct determination of employment status, access to relevant evidence within the control of the platforms must also be ensured (Article 16). Furthermore, protection from adverse treatment or consequences resulting from complaints lodged or proceedings brought against the platforms to ensure compliance with the rights provided for in the directive (Article 17), and protection against dismissal for having exercised those rights (Article 18) must be ensured. A regression by the Member States with respect to the general levels of protection recognized for workers is not permitted (Article 20).

At the moment, the proposal is still being discussed in the Council of the European Union; therefore, it will take some time before it is approved. However, mention should be made of Directive 2019/1152 on transparent and predictable working conditions in the European Union, which aims to improve the conditions of workers by defining minimum rights that apply to all workers in the Union who have a contract of employment or an employment relationship as defined by law, collective agreements or practices in force in each Member State. This also seems to include platform workers (referred to in recital No. 8 of the preamble), who should enjoy the rights provided by the directive. They also include, according to Article 10, the minimum foreseeability of work, which implies that if the organisation of a worker's work is wholly or largely unforeseeable, the employer may not require the worker to work unless conditions are met that the work is carried out within predetermined hours and days and that the worker is informed by their employer of an assignment with reasonable notice set in accordance with national law, collective agreements or national practice.

It is noteworthy that no reference to the protection of the right to disconnect can be found in the Commission's proposal, even though the European Parliament, shortly before the proposal was tabled and precisely with a view to its preparation, had made it clear that platform workers may be exposed to significant health and safety risks which may affect psychosocial health, and that therefore the European Commission's proposal should have addressed the occupational health and safety of platform workers in line with the Union's legal framework on health and safety, and enable them to exercise their rights, including the right to disconnect.⁵³

⁵³ European Parliament resolution of 16 September 2021 on fair working conditions, rights and social protection for platform workers – new forms of employment linked to digital development (2019/2186(INI)), paragraph 14.

10. Conclusion

The use of remote working, in Italy and elsewhere, was originally limited, probably due to a managerial culture not ready for this change and still tied to the idea of centralisation and on-site control of workers.⁵⁴

The Covid-19 pandemic gave a decisive push towards rethinking the relationship between worker and workplace, since the use of remote forms of work made it possible to reconcile the needs of health protection and the economy, i.e. to respect the limitations placed on freedom of movement and, at the same time, to allow productive activities to be carried out.

It was argued that the one implemented in Italy from the early 2020s would be “an extreme and forced experimentation of remote working”, given that workers were not allowed to choose where to work, being de facto bound to stay at home.⁵⁵

As undeniable as this fact is, it is equally undeniable that in Italy, as well as in the legal systems of other European States, legislation has been in place – sometimes for years – that favours work outside the workplace. From home working to teleworking to flexible working, labour law has long since acquired categories that imply a different approach to the relationship between worker and organisation. The Covid-19 pandemic has given a decisive boost to the application of such legislation, thus providing the – tragic – opportunity to try to innovate.

The question now is whether, once the state of emergency is over, remote working will become firmly entrenched on the operational level, thus becoming the norm for a growing number of workers and companies. A rethink of the existing situation is obviously needed. Indeed, agile working requires project-based work organisation divided into phases, paths and cycles.⁵⁶ It must be said that an increasing number of tasks in the new knowledge-based economy can be performed anywhere and at any time as long as the proper technological supports are available, while there are fewer and fewer activities that necessarily require the worker to be on site.⁵⁷

The trend is gaining momentum. In the United States of America, it appears that although workers are aware of the negative aspects of teleworking, especially the propensity to work longer hours, a clear majority of them (between 79 and 87 per cent, depending on the sector considered) declare that they are interested in working remotely at least part of the time. Several studies also show that more than one third of workers would give up part of their salary for having the possibility of teleworking⁵⁸. As for the European Union, the potential of teleworking is estimated at 40%, with an average deployment of 24% already in 2021.⁵⁹

The positive effects seem undeniable, both in terms of productivity and work organisation and, for example, in terms of environmental protection, since remote working reduces commuting and the energy consumption resulting from the equipment needed for work, as well as the heating and cooling of offices.⁶⁰

There is something, however, that is not going to change. As repeatedly emphasised in this report, a person who works outside the company premises enjoys the same rights as a comparable worker

⁵⁴ On this topic, B. CARUSO, L. ZAPPALÀ, *Un diritto del lavoro “tridimensionale”*: valori e tecniche di fronte ai mutamenti dei

luoghi di lavoro, in R. DEL PUNTA (a cura di), *Valori e tecniche nel diritto del lavoro*, Florence, 2022, p. 29 ss.

⁵⁵ <https://www.som.polimi.it/lo-smart-working-ai-tempi-del-coronavirus/>.

⁵⁶ P. POLLIANI, A. COLDESINA, *Lo smart working in Italia tra rivoluzione culturale, normativa emergenziale e un futuro ancora da scrivere*, in *Rivista italiana di informatica e diritto*, 2022, p. 323-324.

⁵⁷ L. GSCHWIND, O. VARGAS, *Telework and its effects in Europe*, in J.C. MESSENGER, *Telework in the 21st Century*, Cheltenham, 2019, p. 37.

⁵⁸ K. LISTER, T. HARNISH, *Telework and its effects in the United States*, in J.C. MESSENGER, cit., p. 129.

⁵⁹ P. SOLER, *The hidden inequalities of telework across the EU*, in *EUObserver*, 4 maggio 2023.

⁶⁰ *Ibidem*.

working on the company's premises. Hence, no forms of discrimination can be allowed that undermine the status of those who work remotely.

At the same time, however, it is necessary to be aware that the condition of those who work outside the premises of the company is not fully overlapping with that of the traditional worker. Therefore, specific modes of protection must be defined for this purpose. The right to disconnect is an emblematic example of what has just been said.

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